

Design and Fabrication of Compressed Air Engine Technology

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Abstract – *The environmental pollution in the cities is increasing rapidly mostly because of the increased number of fossil fuel powered vehicles. Many alternatives are now being studied throughout the world. One of the solutions can be a compressed air powered vehicle. This work focuses on the conversion of the SI engine to the compressed air engine. A four stroke single cylinder SI engine is converted to operate using compressed air because of its design simplicity. The cylinder head of the engine is modified by removing the existing valve mechanism and replace with a solenoid actuated inlet valve and non-return valve actuated exhaust passages. The engine is tested for the various valves opening and closing for different timings of the valve openings. The compressed air of required pressure is obtained from the compressor. We learned the method of developing camshaft and the valve timing techniques.*

Keywords: *Alternate Fuel, Compressed Air Engine, Valve timing for engine.*

I. Introduction

Gasoline is already the fuel of the past. It might not seem that way as you fill up on your way to work, but the petroleum used to make it is gradually running out. It also pollutes air that's becoming increasingly unhealthy to breathe, and people no longer want to pay the high prices that oil companies are charging for it [1]. Automobile manufacturers know all of this and have spent lots of time and money to find and develop the fuel of the future [2-3].

The search is on, but what will this fuel of the future be? Ready-made fuels like petroleum are becoming more difficult to find and automobile manufacturers are turning to greener energy sources like batteries. These batteries can be charged with energy and placed in a car where that energy can be released. As good as that idea might seem, some manufacturers think air could become an even better energy source [4-6].

Air? At first glance, the idea of running a car on air seems almost too good to be true. If we can use air as fuel, why think about using anything else? Air is all around us. Air never runs out. Air is non-polluting. Best of all, air is free [8-9].

I.1. Objective

In this work compressed air engine, we have used fuel as the compressed air and the four stroke SI is altered to work as a compressed air engine. In the conversion of commercial SI engine to a compressed air engine we have altered the engine head by removing the cam shaft and valve arrangement, and made the valve function by placing the solenoid valve with the timer circuit because

of the difficulty faced in changing the design of the cam shaft in the inlet direction and by placing a non-return valve in the exhaust direction to avoid the return of the compressed air into the engine while suction.

I.2. Application

- Air driven engines can be used as drives for different types of conveyors such as Belt conveyors, Chain conveyors, Screw conveyors, etc., It is normally used for slow speed conveyors. Medium load can only be used.
- Displacement pumps of low pressure capacities.
- MDI makes MultiCATs vehicle that can be used as buses or trucks. RATP has also already expressed an interest in the compressed-air pollution-free bus.
- Compressed air locomotives have been historically used as mining locomotives and in various areas.

I.3. Advantages

- Compressed air to power a car's engine is that a pure compressed air vehicle produces no pollution, there is no harmful gases such as carbon dioxide
- Air cars are also designed to be lighter than conventional cars, due to the absence of fuel mixing parts and fuel carrying parts the weight of the vehicle is considerably less.
- Advantage of air cars is that the fuel should be remarkably cheap. The air can be directly absorbed from nature easily and there is no cost for it the only the cost of the fuel is to compress the air.

- Considering the other type of fossil fuel vehicles the compressed air engine is relatively low cost. Due to the simple construction the vehicle cost is low.
- No frequent filling of fuel, if the compressor is inbuilt in the vehicle itself then it can be used for the production of compressed air then there is no refilling the fuel in the stations

II. Designing of Compressed Air Engine - Vehicle

Fig. 1. Air Path across the components

II.1. Brake Power

The brake power of an engine is the useful power available at the crank shaft of the engine for doing external work. This power is less than the actual power (indicated power) developed by the engine cylinder. Measurement of the brake power is done by rope brake arrangement or by prony brake arrangement.

$$\text{Break power} = \frac{2\pi NT}{60}$$

where N be Speed in rpm = 300rpm

T be Resistance torque acting on the brake drum

Model Calculation:

$$T = (W - S) * \left(\frac{D+t}{2}\right) g$$

Where W be Load applied on the rope = 17kg

S be Spring balance reading = 0.1kg

D be Diameter of the brake drum = 110mm

t be Thickness = 5mm

g be Acceleration due to gravity = 9.81 m/s²

$$T = 9.53 \text{ Nm}$$

$$\text{B.P} = \frac{(2\pi * 300 * 9.53)}{60} = 0.3 \text{ KW}$$

II.2. Specific fuel Consumption

It is defined as the amount of fuel consumed per unit power developed per hour.

$$\text{Volume of the engine cylinder } V = \frac{\pi d^2 * L}{4} / 60 \text{ m}^3 / \text{s}$$

Where d- Diameter of the cylinder = 50mm

L- Length of the cylinder = 110mm

$$\text{Therefore } V = 3.59 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 / \text{s}$$

$$\text{Volume of the storage tank } V = \frac{\pi d^2 * L}{4}$$

Where d- Diameter of the tank = 200mm

$$L\text{- Length of the tank} = 750 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Therefore } V = 0.023 \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{Vehicle running hour} = \frac{\text{Volume of the tank}}{\text{Volume of the engine cylinder}}$$

$$= \frac{0.023}{3.59 * 10^{-6}}$$

$$= 6406 \text{ s}$$

$$= 2 \text{ hr } 17 \text{ min}$$

II.3. Design of Vehicle Frame

Fig. 2. Vehicle Frame

Bending moment - Bending moment at a cross section of a beam may be defined as the algebraic sum of the moment of the forces to the right or left of the section.

Shear force - Shear force at a cross section of a beam may be defined as unbalanced vertical forces to the right or left of the section.

Fig. 3. Vehicle Frame_ SFD and BMD

Sum of upward forces = sum of downward forces

$$\begin{aligned} R_a + R_b &= (148 * 0.110) + (79 * 0.15) \\ &= 16.28 + 11.85 \\ &= 28.13\text{N} \end{aligned}$$

Moment from the left support

$$\begin{aligned} (R_b * 1.100) - (148 * 0.110 * ((110/2) + 0.645)) \\ &= (79 * 0.15 * ((0.15/2) + 0.1)) \\ (R_b * 1.100) &= (16.28 * 0.7) + 2.073 \\ R_b &= 12.24\text{N} \\ (R_a + R_b) &= 28.13 \\ (R_a + 12.24) &= 28.13 \\ R_a &= 15.89\text{N} \end{aligned}$$

Bending moment

$$\begin{aligned} \text{B.M at C} &= 0\text{N} \\ \text{B.M at B} &= 0\text{N} \\ \text{B.M at D} &= (13 * 0.345) = 4.485\text{N} \\ \text{B.M at E} &= (13 * 0.345) - (148 * 0.11 * (0.11/2)) \\ &= 5.01\text{Nm} \\ \text{B.M at F} &= (13 * 0.850) - (148 * 0.11 * ((0.11/2) + 0.395)) \\ &= 3.724 \\ \text{B.M at G} &= (13 * 1.100) - (148 * 0.11 * ((0.11/2) + 0.545)) - (79 * 0.15 * (0.150/2)) \\ &= 4.12\text{N} \\ \text{B.M at A} &= (13 * 1.100) - (148 * 0.11 * ((0.11/2) + 0.645)) - (79 * 0.15 * ((0.150/2) + 0.1)) \\ &= 0\text{Nm} \end{aligned}$$

Shear force

$$\begin{aligned} \text{S.F at C} &= 0\text{N} \\ \text{S.F at B} &= -13\text{N} \\ \text{S.F at D} &= -13\text{N} \\ \text{S.F at E} &= -13 + (148 * 0.11) \\ &= 3.28\text{N} \\ \text{S.F at F} &= 3.28\text{N} \\ \text{S.F at G} &= 3.28 + (79 * 0.15) \\ &= 15.89\text{N} \\ \text{S.F at R}_a &= 15.89\text{N (without reaction)} \\ \text{S.F at R}_a &= 15.89 - 15.89 \\ &= 0\text{N} \end{aligned}$$

The shear force is maximum at the point G and the Bending moment is maximum at the point G.

II.4. Design of Chain Drive

Fig. 4. Chain Drive

Chain drives are used to transmit power between two parallel shafts comparatively at a longer distance. The chain drive is between the belt drives in between the belt

drives and gear drives. Simple chain drive consists of two sprockets and an endless chain. Smaller is called pinion and the bigger one is called wheel.

Calculation

Step 1: Selection of speed ratio

$$\text{Speed ratio } i = Z_2/Z_1 = 1$$

Z₂ – Number of teeth in the wheel = 18

Z₁ – Number of teeth in the sprocket pinion = 18

Step 2: Selection of pitch of the chain

Centre distance = a = (30 to 50)p

Where a - Centre distance = 350mm

p- Pitch of the chain (40p = 350)

therefore p=11.6mm

Selecting the standard pitch of the chain p =

12.7mm from the standard data book

Step 3: Selection of chain type

From the data book for the pitch 12.7mm and the type of chain as simplex tube.

ISO/DIN = 082-1

Rolon = R1224

Roller diameter = 7.75mm

Bearing are A = 0.17cm²

Weight per meter w = 0.28kgf

Breaking load Q = 820kgf

Step 4: Selection of force acting on the chain

$$\sum P = P_t + P_c + P_s$$

where

P_t- tangential force due to power transmission Kgf

$$P_t = 102\text{N}/v = 17\text{kgf}$$

Where N - Power produced by engine cylinder

v- Velocity of chain m/s

P_c- centrifugal tension Kgf

$$P_c = wv^2 / g = 0.036\text{kgf}$$

Where w – weight per meter kgf

P_s- tension due to sagging of chain, Kgf

$$P_s = k * w * a = 0.392\text{kgf}$$

Where k – coefficient of sag = 4

a be centre distance

$$\text{Therefore } \sum P = 17.428 \text{ kgf}$$

Step 5: Selection of load on shaft

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= K_t * P \\ &= 1.3 * 12.7 \\ &= 22.1\text{kgf} \end{aligned}$$

Step 6: Calculation of service factor

$$K_s = K_1 * K_2 * K_3 * K_4 * K_5 * K_6$$

From the standard data book

K₁ = Load factor for variable loads and heavy shocks = 1.5

K₂ = Distance factor regulation for fixed centre distance = 1.5

K₃ = Factor of centre distance of sprockets = 0.8

$$\begin{aligned} lp &= 2ap + \left(\frac{Z_1 + Z_2}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{Z_2 - Z_1}{ap} \right) \\ &= 2 * 27.6 + \left(\frac{18 + 18}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{18 - 18}{27.6} \right) \\ &= 73.3\text{mm} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Length of the chain} &= l_p * p \\ &= 73.3 * 12.7 \\ &= 940\text{mm} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Corrected center distance} &= \frac{e + \sqrt{e^2 - 8m}}{4} \\ &= \frac{56 + \sqrt{56^2 - 8 * 1}}{4} \\ &= 356\text{mm} \end{aligned}$$

K4- factor for the position of sprockets for up to 60degree = 1.5

K5- lubrication factor for periodic = 1.5

K6- rating factor for continuous running = 1.5

$$K_s = 1.5 * 1.5 * 0.8 * 1.5 * 1.5 * 1.5 = 3.375$$

Step 7: Checking for factor of safety

Power transmitted on the basis of breaking load

$$\begin{aligned} N &= Q.v / (102 * n * K_s) \\ &= 820 * 1.25 / (102 * n * 3.375) \end{aligned}$$

$$n = 13$$

Design is safe minimum factor of safety for 300 rpm is 8.55

Step 8: Calculation of allowable bearing stress

Power transmitted on the basis of bearing stress

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \sigma * A * v / (102 * K_s) \\ 0.3 &= \sigma * 0.17 * 1.25 / (102 * 3.375) \end{aligned}$$

$$\sigma = 2.05 * ([10]^{-3} \text{Kgf}) / (\text{cm}^2)$$

Design of power transmission done for the requirement and safely.

II.5. Circuit

Fig. 5. Solenoid valve

Fig. 6. Electrical circuit is designed for actuating the spool of the solenoid valve

The electrical circuit is designed for actuating the spool of the solenoid valve. In this circuit it consists of a LED, LDR, Resistors, Transistors, Relay, DC supply, and a Relay.

The LED is connected to the DC supply of 5V through a resistance. A LDR is placed in front of the LED. The LDR is connected with the 12V DC supply through the 1kΩ resistance. The output of the LDR is connected to the relay. The collector end of the transistor is connected to the DC supply, Base is connected with the supply. Output of the, that is emitter is connected to the relay. A solenoid valve is connected with the relay.

When the supply is given to the LED it emits the light to the air. LDR which is placed in front of the LED receives the light emitted by the LED. Whenever the LDR is in actuation the supply to the relay through the transmitter is obstructed. So there is no output to the solenoid valve. If the LDR doesn't receive the light rays the output from the LDR is disconnected so the power supply from the 12v DC is passed to the relay through the transistor to the ground so the relay is activated. The relay coil connects the normally open circuit and the supply is given to it. The output that is the solenoid coil one end is connected to the relay normally open end receives the power and the solenoid gets actuated, and the air is supplied to the engine. The placing of LDR and LED is based on the flywheel rotation and on the basis of valve opening position and valve closing position.

III. Problem Findings

III.1. Engine

Making a thread in the inlet and exhaust passage of the engine is a very difficult task because the standard size of tapping tool cannot find for our requirement size. And the other major problem in tapping a thread is the material of the engine is aluminium and it can be hold in a position by using the holding devices. Valve, cam shaft and timing gear assemblies already present in the engine is removed to make the engine to work in two strokes. After the removal of the valve from the port there is hole provision to guide the valve in opening and closing. To close the guide passage, it is another difficult task if the hole is not closed there will be air leakage which affects the engine performance. Selection of suitable size of the non-return valve because it should be available for the thread size we make in the engine ports. The non-return valve is available in one standard and the tapping size is in another standard. Balancing the fly wheel is the another task to make the piston move from the bottom dead centre to the top dead centre the balancing is difficult. Connecting the sprocket to the engine crank shaft. The bore of the sprocket is larger than the diameter of the extended shaft from the crank shaft.

III.2. Vehicle Frame

Selecting the frame shape is difficult because its weight should not be more and at the same time it should withstand the load and thrust created due to the engine running. Design of the position of the engine and tank because to maintain the traction effectively the weight balancing should be designed perfectly

III.3. Performance of Engine

In the first testing of the engine we provided both sides as non-return valve there is a problem of closing the valve while the piston moving from the bottom dead centre to the top dead centre. Then we provided the solenoid valve in the inlet side for that we need a timing electronic circuit for the valve opening and closing for the actuation. In that timing circuit it is constant timing circuit so there is a problem if the speed of the engine is increased it will create the knocking in the engine. Then we go for an IR sensor circuit which will actuate the solenoid valve, in that circuit we faced a big problem.

IV. Problem Definitions

IV.1. Engine

We have received a large size tapping tool which suits to our non-return valve also. We have enlarged the hole with the standard size thread and we connected the non-return valve with the engine using connectors. But in the exhaust side it cannot be tapped so we pasted the metal with tapped inside with the standard size with the help of metal adhesives.

Fig. 7. Fabricated Engine

In the guide line of the valve we planned to insert an oversized aluminium bar but it is difficult because guide path is not of same cross section. So again we use adhesive material to fill in the gap and it is permanently closed. Once we made the standard size thread in the engine we surveyed the various connectors to connect the engine and non-return valve and we finally got the connectors of required diameter and the problem was solved. Balancing the flywheel is difficult we have done many calculation to balance the flywheel but is very difficult so we are still founding

the solution to overcome this problem and we are extending this project to the next level in the final years between this year we surely found a way to overcome this difficulty. Connecting the sprocket with the engine shaft we have searched many sprockets which has minimum bore diameter but we could not found the sprocket with our requirement. So we have machined a bush like arrangement in the cast iron material and we have bored and turned to the require size and inserted in the sprocket and installed in the crank shaft of the engine.

IV.2. Vehicle Frame

We have surveyed a lot to found how should be a frame and finally we got the idea from the cycle rickshaw and we analyzed how the frame is built and what cross section is selected for building the frame. And finally we have selected the L type cross sectioned frame is selected. We have built the frame in foundry laboratory by using the arc welding machine and metal cutting machines in the machine shop laboratories to machine the metal bushes. After the vehicle is built we have placed the tank and engine in various positions and we finally designed the position these decision is made manually. Welding of the wheel shaft with the chassis is done with the medium of bearing. First we have inserted the wheel sprocket in to the shaft and position it in correct position according to our requirement and then the bearings are inserted in the two ends of the shaft and the bearing is welded with the chassis.

V. Cost Estimation

Sl.No	Particular	Fabrication Cost
1.	Engine	1000
2.	Compressed air tank	450
3.	Non return valve	500
4.	Solenoid valve	650
4.	Vehicle frame construction	1200
5.	Wheels and bearing	520
6.	Connectors and travelling charges	650
	Total cost	4970/- Rs

VI. Conclusion

The model created by us is a small scale working model of the compressed air engine. When scaled to the larger level it can be used for automobiles as independent or combined as a hybrid system with the IC engines. We have tested the engine with many possible starting circuits for the starting of the compressed air engine and we have found many results that how the engine is starting and what are all the failures founded in each testing's. The all possible way of resolving the failure is going on.

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